

Traditional therapeutic use of the earthworm *Eisenia fetida* and exploration of its anti-tumour potential against Ascites Dalton's lymphoma cells in Swiss albino mice

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Traditional knowledge-based medicine has gained worldwide attention, and presently the scientific community is focusing on the proper scientific validation and identification of major compounds to incorporate in the formulation of modern medicine for the treatment of various diseases. The North East region of India is the home of various ethnic groups with unique cultures, traditions, and indigenous medicinal knowledge systems. Here, the indigenous people most often use different animal parts and their byproducts similarly to plant-based medicine in their traditional medicinal preparation. Earthworm *Eisenia fetida*, commonly known as the red earthworm, is one of the most significant medicinal animals used by traditional healers in different communities for the treatment of various diseases like pneumonia, vocal cord infection, cough, and cancer-related suspected diseases. The present study was aimed at exploring the potential anticancer effects of *Eisenia fetida* paste/extract (EFP) against Ascites Dalton's lymphoma cells in vivo condition in Swiss albino mice. The EFP extract demonstrated a significant antitumour effect, possibly by initiating programmed cell death and mitochondrial changes in the tumour cells. The viability of tumour cells exhibited a reduction over time due to EFP treatment. EFP treatment was found to show a progressive increase in the quantity of apoptotic DL cells over time, suggesting a time-dependent impact on the induction of apoptosis in the treated groups. These results imply that EFP might serve as a safer substitute for cancer treatment and hold promise for developing new and improved therapeutic strategies against cancer. It suggests a promising avenue for developing new and improved therapeutic strategies against cancer, with the potential to enhance treatment outcomes while minimizing adverse effects. However, further experimentation is required to elucidate the active principles and molecular mechanisms of apoptotic pathways.

Keyword: Traditional, *Eisenia fetida*, Dalton's lymphoma, antitumour.